

SZ-100

Measurement Results

Date : 14 June 2025 14:03:45
Measurement Type : Particle Size
Sample Name : A2
Scattering Angle : 90
Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 2.012 mPa·s
Transmission Intensity before Meas. : 25321
Distribution Form : Standard
Distribution Form(Dispersity) : Monodisperse
Representation of Result : Scattering Light Intensity
Count Rate : 171 kCPS

Calculation Results

Peak No.	S.P.Area Ratio	Mean	S. D.	Mode
1	1.00	781 nm	35 nm	67 nm
2	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
3	---	--- nm	--- nm	--- nm
Total	1.00	781 nm	35 nm	67 nm

Cumulant Operations

Z-Average : 776 nm
PI : 0.623

